

**EFFECT OF WHOLE LANGUAGE APPROACH (WLA) ON LEARNING READING SKILLS
AMONGST PUPILS IN OBASANJO MODEL SCHOOL HWOLSHE JOS, PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of the Whole Language Approach (WLA) on sight word vocabulary and reading comprehension of learners who are non-readers in Obasanjo Inclusive Model Primary School 'B' Hwolshe, Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria. The problem of the research originated from the review of problems arising from reading and writing performance amongst pupils within the regular school setting. Literature has it that the learners have problems with sight words recognition and reading comprehension. The study utilized the Smith (1973) psycholinguistic theory. Two research questions guided the study through experimental pretest-posttest design. The study population was largely non-readers in primaries four and five. The sample for intervention comprised ten (10) Non-readers adopted as a purposive sample. The instruments were the Sight Word Recognition Test and Comprehension Passages from Extension Model English for primary schools (UBE Edition) 4 and 5. The treatment package consisted of a Whole Language Approach and the intervention programme involved Sight Word recognition and Reading comprehension. The stability and internal consistency of the instruments were 0.75 (SW) and 0,85 (RC & CS) respectively. Gain score and mean scores were employed for data analysis. The results showed that Whole Language Approach is a powerful tool for enhancing the learning and literacy skills of non-readers, (Sight Word Recognition of the non-readers as well as Reading Comprehension. The researcher recommended that the Whole Language Approach be adopted to enhance Sight Word Recognition and Reading Comprehension Skills of non-readers in inclusive schools in Nigeria.

Keywords: Whole Language Approach (WLA); Sight Word Recognition; Reading Comprehension Skills

Introduction

Learning activities are means through which learners are guided towards acquiring reading abilities. Reading plays a crucial function in the school learning environment. Inability to read at any level be it literal, inferential, or critical levels affects the main aim of attending school in the first place. Reading creates a solid footing and inspiration for learners' development and education at the heart of reading is comprehension and comprehension hinges on the enriching sight word vocabulary and recognition of such, without which reading comprehension has not taken place. Alongside, sight weed vocabulary, reading comprehension is copying and eligible writing skills (Babudoh & Iheanacho 2015; Gomwalk, 2018).

In order to meaningfully develop Sight Word Recognition (SWR) and Reading Comprehension (RC) of non-readers that are within the regular school and are regular school learners (Landis, Umolu & Mancha 2010; Gomwalk, 2018) recommended crosslinguistic procedure in reading and writing development, thereby endorsing the use of Whole Language Approach (WLA) instructional methodology. This technique portrays and also stands for an innovational and wholistic way of inculcating and learning reading comprehension which lays more special weight on the gaining and acquiring of primary skills of reading and writing.

Word Recognition: Sight Word recognitions are vocabulary that are commonly used by the learners to appreciate printed materials. It is also essential to give primary focus to sight word recognition development. One main purpose for this is that vocabulary knowledge is essentially critical to reading. Words are the cornerstone and building blocks of comprehension. This exposes and explains why recognition is the understructure of the reading process, and reading and writing development. The entire aim of reading is indeed comprehension, but without the ability to recognize individual words in test materials quickly and correctly, this aim cannot be attained (Ikwen, 2013, Ozegya, 2015). It can be said that sight words are the bonds that hold concepts, ideas, and content together thereby making comprehension accessible and attainable to learners. Combs (2006) opined that meaningful words are more forthcoming for learners and readers to retain and remember. The first words pupils can read are those usually experienced already in their environment and are familiar with. This is because they have linked the discriminating attributes of these words to personal activities. Meanwhile, in the event, that pupils come across unfamiliar words experience them through repeated exposure at different times. They are likely to infer its possible meaning from the context. The context enables pupils to make suggestions or viewpoints towards word meaning and to watch and verify prognosis (Greenwood & Flannigan, 2007, Nelson 2008). Doing so would have satisfied the whole essence of reading comprehension.

Reading comprehension is a means of gaining meaning from a text material. The aim of every reading activity is eventually to help the reader comprehend text material. Comprehension is not passive but an interactive, intentional, thinking process by which the reader establishes meaning. Ojo (2011) described reading comprehension as involving at least two or more people: the reader(s) and the writer(s). The process of comprehending involves decoding the author's (s) word and engaging the reader's (s) background experience to build an appropriate understanding of the author's (s) usage. Andzayi and Umolu (2004) viewed reading as the interpretation and comprehension of imprinted or signed texts. It involves the evaluation of the author's (s) mind from the writer's (s) background experiences, with a view of making additions or subtractions from the author's (s) opinion or maintaining such.

A non-reader is seen as one who lacks the ability of a fluent reader. They read below grade level and could struggle with comprehension, phonics, and vocabulary, feeling unable to achieve they might exhibit inappropriate behaviors to hide their inability to read and comprehend. Incidentally, these learners abound in the inclusive education setting and all necessary interventions must be provided to address their problem.

Inclusion education, therefore, means more than simply placing children with disabilities in regular classrooms. It means giving children with disabilities opportunities as members in all school activities and affirming their right to such opportunities. Inclusion is how schools develop and design classrooms, programmes, and activities so that all children can learn and participate together in the neighborhood school system. Neighborhood schools are part of our communities. Inclusive Development Foundation (IDF) believes they are essential for a quality education system Inclusive education is important because it recognizes diversities among members of the communities. These communities begin at school, where all children learn to live together alongside peers. They learn together, play together, and nurture together. This projects that all children have the right to quality education that caters, to the extent possible, to their individual needs, using appropriate methodology.

The Whole Language Approach (WLA) which was used for the intervention is a method of teaching literacy based on the child's existing experience of language. The approach creates a natural link between receptive language spoken language and written language. It is implemented using the following steps: Generating a story topic, by providing experiences through events, selecting a story topic from the list of events by learners, and dictation of story by learners. The researcher writes down the story dictated, the learner and researcher read the written down story together, the learners are encouraged to illustrate their story, and the learners practice reading their dictated and illustrated story. The study is based on the conceptual framework of the "Crosslinguistic Theoretic mode" of language learning as first propounded by Smith (1973) as applied specifically to reading comprehension learning and teaching. The theoretical model seeks to demonstrate connections between diverse aspects of language learning and with social and psychological habits of learners in general. This framework is based on the underlying reading literacy among children at the basic inclusive education level and has been adopted within this study because it has particular prominence on the flexible patterns of language learning including acquiring sight words, reading comprehension, and coping skills for all learners. It is against this background that this finding is based.

Statement of Problem

The problem of this study has its roots in the observation of problems surrounding aspects of learning and literacy development of learners in the inclusive school setting. Majority of learners in the school have limited vocabulary skills for communication in the English language. They equally find it difficult to read books of their grade level and, thus, have comprehension. It is equally observed that the learners have poor coping skills. These problems significantly affect their receptive and expressive communication skills and require intervention. Limited sight word recognition (SWR) has significant effects on learners' ability to express themselves orally or in written form (Ozeqya, 2015). Observation of SWR, Reading comprehension (RC), and Copying skills (CS) show that the literacy performance of these learners was very poor compared to their class level. This means that the learners need to develop their basic for required academic progression.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of the Whole Language Approach on Sight Word Recognition (SWR) and Reading Comprehension (RC) non-reader in Obasanjo Model School B Hwolshe.

Research Questions

The following research questions were advanced for investigation

1. To what extent would the use of the Whole Language Approach influence sight word recognition skills of non-readers in Primary four and five?
2. To what extent would the use of the Whole Language Approach influence the reading comprehension skills of non-readers in primary four and five?

Methodology

Design

This study is an experimental single-group pretest-posttest design. Here the independent variable was measured once before the treatment was implemented. The independent variable (SWR and RC). The non-readers were pretested, provided intervention, and post-tested.

Population

The population of the study was made up of all non-readers in primary four and five at Obasanjo Model Inclusive Primary School 'B' Hwolshe, Ios Plateau State Ten (10) severe cases of non-readers in primary four and five were adopted as a purposive sample for the study.

Sample Instruments

Similarly, two instruments were employed for data collection in the study namely: (1) Sight Word recognition and comprehension passages adapted from (2) Extension Modern English for primary schools (UBE edition) 4 and 5. The instruments had reliability indices of 0.75 (SWR) and 0.85 (RC), they were used to provide intervention on sight word recognition, reading, and comprehension.

After eight weeks of intervention using the LEA programme, they were post-tested using the same instruments. Consequently, the research questions 1 and 2 were analyzed using gain-scores and mean scores.

Results

- 1. To what extent would the use of WLA influence sight word recondition skills of non-readers in primary four and five**

Table 1: Gain Score on Sight Word Recognition Skills of Learners

S/N	Learners:	pretest	Post-test	Gain Score
1	AA	15	100	85
2	AB	3	55	52
3	AC	10	100	90
4	AD	10	75	65
5	AE	12	80	68
6	AF	6	50	44
7	AG	0	3	3
8	AH	1	20	19
9	AI	8	100	92
10	AJ	5	45	40
Mean		7.00	62.80	

Table one above shows the results obtained from sight word recognition of learners in the inclusive setting. The table shows that the total mean score of the pretest was 7.00, while the posttest was 62.8. This implies that the posttest result is higher than the pretest result after intervention. Thus, the highest score was 92 (AI), while the lowest was 3 (AG).

- 2. To what extent would the use of WLA influence reading comprehension skills of non-readers in primary four and five?**

Table 2: Gain Score on Whole Language Approach Reading Learners ' Comprehension skills.

S/N	Learners:	pretest	posttest	Gain score
1	AA	5	100	95
2	AB	0	75	75
3	AC	5	100	95
4	AD	10	75	65
5	AE	5	75	70
6	AF	0	50	50

7	AG	0	5	5
8	AH	0	50	50
9	AI	10	100	90
10	AJ	0	40	40
Mean		3.50	55.50	

Table two above reveals the results obtained from the reading comprehension skills of the learners in inclusive settings. It shows that the total mean score for the pretest was 3.50, while the posttest was 55.50. Similarly, the highest gain score was 95 (AI and AC) while the lowest gain score was 5 (AG). This implies that the use of WLA has a significant influence on the reading comprehension skills of the learners.

Discussion

The results presented above concern the non-readers in the inclusive education programme in primary four and five. It could be deduced that after 8 weeks of the intervention, the WLA approach improved the performance of non-readers in sight word recognition and reading comprehension. These were indicated by the gain score as well as the mean score of the learners for each of the variables tested. The results also revealed that at the pretest the learner performed below average but after the intervention using the WLA approach their performance improved significantly. These findings corroborate Lere (2013), Bodang (2013), and Gomwalk (2018) supported their previous research findings that non-readers can learn Basic Learning Skills such as reading and writing skills provided an expanded intervention programme is administered after identifying the problem.

Findings

1. The sight recognition skills of the non-readers significantly improved after exposure to the WLA.
2. The finding revealed that the reading comprehension skills of the non-readers significantly improved after exposure to the WLA instruction.

Recommendations

1. Teachers should encourage Non-readers to practice reading individual words found in textbooks, magazines, and boards among others.
2. Teachers, especially those of non-readers should adopt the WLA as a method of teaching reading to non-readers in schools.
3. The government through SUBEB should set specific reading classes/centres in inclusive schools/communities for the sole purpose of teaching reading to non-readers using WLA.
4. Parent should give their wards the opportunity to practice reading on their own through stories and making word-bank. This will increase their word reservoir as well as build their sight word vocabulary.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares that they have no conflict of interest.

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Authors and Levels of Contributions

Dr. Nenrot V. Gomwalk thought up a little of the work, designed the study, wrote the introduction, and purpose, and compiled the manuscript. She generated the research questions. She did the conclusion and recommendation part.

Mr. Gomos P. Obadiah handled the statistical analysis, data compilation, and discussion.

Disclaimer Statement

We the authors declare that this article is a newly developed research work. It has not been indicated by in-text citations and full bibliographic details are given in the references.

References

- Combs, M. M. (2006). *An observational survey of early literacy achievement* (2nd ed.). Portsmouth, N.H: Heinemann.
- Babudoh, (I. B. & Iheanacho, J. I. (2015). The use of quantum magnetic resonance image analyzer to determine the effects of trace element levels on special needs children with reading disabilities. *International Journal of Literacy. Development*, 1. (1), 137-146
- Gomwalk. N. V. (2018). *Effects of language experience approach on literacy skills of learners with intellectual (disabilities, in Jos metropolis, Plateau state*. University of Jos: PhD thesis
- Greenwood, C. R... Delquadri, J., & Hall. R. V. (1984). Opportunity to respond and student academic, performance. In: W. Heward, T. Heron, D. Hall & .I. Trap-Porter (Eds.). *Behavior analysis in education*. Columbus, OH: Merrill.
- Ikwen'. E. U. (2013). *Effects of concentrated language encounter methods in developing beginning reading skills in primary school pupils in Cross'-River State*. Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, University of Jos.
- Landis. D': Umolu. J. & Mancha. S. (2010). The power of language experience for cross-cultural reading and wilting. *The Reading Teacher*, 6, 580-589
- Lere. M. M. (2013). *Mental retardation*. University of Jos: Unpublished postgraduate lecture
- Ojo. G. (2011). *Reading in content area*. Unpublished Monograph, Department of- Arts Education, University of Jos.,
- Ozegya. A. E. (2015). *Effects of students and teachers actively reading text strategy on reading comprehension of students with hearing impairment in Jos, Plateau state*. . Unpublished PhD thesis: University of Jos.
- Smith, T. E. (1973). *Teaching students with special needs in inclusive settings*. New York: Allyn and Bacon.
- Umolu, J. J. (2004). Whole language literacy instruction in primary schools. An innovative response to widespread reading failure. In: C. T. O. Akinmade and T. O. Oyetunde (Eds.). *Journal of Educational Improvement*. Nigeria: West African Council for Educational Improvement.